

TOWARDS EXPERT FINANCIAL QA VIA SELF-IMPROVING RAG

Junjie Xiong

University of California, Berkeley

ABSTRACT

Expert financial question answering over SEC filings demands numeric faithfulness and auditable provenance, yet single-pass RAG systems silently hallucinate figures and offer no mechanism to recognize their own failures. Compounding this, financial deployments operate under a *walled garden* constraint: web-search fallbacks used by prior corrective RAG methods are prohibited by data governance. We present **Self-Improving RAG**, a training-free framework that decomposes document QA into three specialized agents (Retrieval, Reasoning, Judge) coordinated by an orchestrator with feedback-driven retry. When the Judge scores an answer below a dynamic threshold, the system escalates in place, broader retrieval, more careful prompting, and relaxed acceptance, never leaving the authorized corpus. On FinanceBench, our approach reaches **86%** accuracy under oracle-guided evaluation (up from 53% single-pass) with a **36.4%** Lazarus Rate, recovering nearly four in ten initially wrong answers. We additionally report an honest caveat: under fully blind deployment the same judge accepts only **31%**, exposing judge quality, not the retry loop, as the true bottleneck for regulated finance QA.

1 INTRODUCTION

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) has become the standard paradigm for knowledge-intensive question answering (Lewis et al., 2020), yet its deployment in high-stakes domains such as finance (Islam et al., 2023; Tai et al., 2025) exposes a critical gap: conventional single-pass pipelines cannot recognize, let alone recover from, their own failures (Asai et al., 2024; Yan et al., 2024). Consider a financial analyst querying SEC filings for quarterly revenue: a single-pass system retrieves, generates, and returns, with no mechanism to verify correctness and no trace of how the answer was formed. For financial professionals, a wrong answer is worse than no answer, and an answer without an **audit trail** is indistinguishable from a guess.

The Walled Garden Constraint. Financial applications impose a constraint absent in general-domain QA: retrieval must remain within authorized document corpora. Unlike methods that fall back to web search when initial retrieval fails (Yan et al., 2024), financial QA operates in a “walled garden” where data governance prohibits external sources, eliminating a common recovery mechanism. This closed-domain restriction simultaneously acts as an *agent governance mechanism*, guaranteeing that every answer traces to authorized, auditable evidence, a prerequisite for deploying agentic systems in regulated industries.

In finance specifically, three additional challenges compound: (1) *numeric reasoning* over tables and financial statements, (2) *temporal filtering* requiring understanding of fiscal years and reporting periods, and (3) *entity disambiguation* among ticker symbols, subsidiaries, and corporate name changes.

Our Approach. We propose **Self-Improving RAG**, a training-free framework that decomposes document QA into three specialized agents coordinated by an orchestrator with feedback-driven self-correction. A **Retrieval Agent** selects and escalates retrieval pipelines with attempt number; a **Reasoning Agent** generates cited answers and adapts its prompting strategy; and a **Judge Agent** scores answers against a dynamic threshold and decides whether to accept or retry. The key insight is that when a first attempt fails, the system *escalates in place*, retrieving more documents, prompting

Figure 1: Three-agent architecture: Retrieval, Reasoning, and Judge agents coordinated by an Orchestrator. When score $s_1 < \tau$, our system retries with escalated retrieval ($k:10 \rightarrow 20 \rightarrow 30$) and adapted prompting until accepted or budget exhausted.

more carefully, and relaxing acceptance once effort has been spent, rather than returning a low-quality answer. This contrasts with prior adaptive retrieval (Jeong et al., 2024; Asai et al., 2024) that focuses on initial routing without recovery, and with prior single-model self-correction (Madaan et al., 2023) that lacks specialized agents for diagnosing whether failure originated in retrieval or reasoning.

Our contributions toward expert-level financial QA are:

1. **Structured Self-Correction for Document QA:** Unlike prior single-model self-reflection (Madaan et al., 2023), we introduce *targeted escalation* across retrieval, generation, and evaluation stages, with specialized agents diagnosing whether failure originated in retrieval or reasoning.
2. **Grounded Verification:** A Judge that performs entailment checking against retrieved evidence, augmented with programmatic numeric verification for financial figures.
3. **Audit-First Design:** Every agent decision is logged with provenance, confidence scores, and reasoning traces, enabling the compliance review required by regulated industries.
4. **Honest Oracle-vs-Deployment Evaluation:** We evaluate the same system under two protocols, an oracle-guided judge (with gold-answer access, for comparison with prior work) and a fully blind deployment judge. Reporting both reveals the judge, not the retry loop, as the deployment bottleneck and avoids the optimistic framing common in self-correcting RAG.

On FinanceBench, Self-Improving RAG reaches **86%** correctness under oracle-guided evaluation (vs. 53% single-pass) with a **36.4%** Lazarus Rate, recovering nearly 4 in 10 initially incorrect answers through targeted retry. Under fully blind deployment the same judge accepts only **31%**, a gap we report transparently: the retry mechanism is effective, but ungrounded quality estimation limits what any closed-domain system can confidently release without human review. A further finding is that a fixed retrieval pipeline with judge-driven retry matches dynamic routing while preserving full interpretability, suggesting that for regulated domains the correction loop is more valuable than learned routing.

2 RELATED WORK

Self-Correction and Agentic RAG. Agentic RAG embeds autonomous agents into retrieval pipelines to enable self-correction beyond single-pass systems (Singh et al., 2025). Reflexion (Shinn et al., 2023) uses verbal reinforcement across episodes, while Self-Refine (Madaan et al., 2023) applies single-model critique-refine loops. Self-RAG (Asai et al., 2024) fine-tunes models to emit reflection tokens, and CRAG (Yan et al., 2024) triggers corrective web retrieval on failure. Self-correction can also be learned via RL (Kumar et al., 2025), which defines a *correction rate* metric conceptually related to our Lazarus Rate. Unlike Reflexion, we correct *within a single session*; unlike Self-Refine, we use *specialized agents* with role-specific verification; unlike Self-RAG and Kumar et al., we require *no fine-tuning or RL training*; unlike CRAG, we never escape the authorized corpus. Crucially, our Judge Agent diagnoses whether failure originated in retrieval *or* reasoning and triggers targeted escalation, unifying both correction modalities.

Adaptive Retrieval, LLM Judges, and Financial RAG. Adaptive-RAG (Jeong et al., 2024) routes queries to pipelines based on complexity but lacks a recovery mechanism. We instead pair a fixed pipeline with judge-driven retry, providing simpler and more explainable behavior for regulated domains. LLM-as-Judge (Zheng et al., 2023) enables scalable quality assessment; recent surveys highlight judge biases (Li et al., 2024) that motivate our separate Judge Agent with entailment checks, and Agent-as-a-Judge (Zhuge et al., 2024) reports 90% human agreement via multi-turn evaluation, supporting our iterative feedback loop. In the financial domain, VeritasFi (Tai et al., 2025) proposes a multi-tiered RAG framework for multi-modal financial QA; our contribution is orthogonal, focusing on judge-driven self-correction and audit trails rather than tiered retrieval. General multi-agent frameworks such as AutoGen (Wu et al., 2024) and MetaGPT (Hong et al., 2024) pioneered LLM coordination, but we tailor agent roles specifically to document QA with finance-domain verification and audit requirements.

Positioning: The Walled Garden Constraint. Our key distinction is the strict *closed-domain* constraint: retrieval must remain within authorized documents, precluding the web-search fallbacks used by CRAG and similar systems that violate financial data-governance policies. This constraint eliminates the most common recovery mechanism and forces self-correction to come from *within* the corpus via escalated retrieval and targeted re-prompting. Table 1 summarizes how Self-Improving RAG relates to prior methods along four dimensions critical for financial deployment, with **Closed-Domain** as the column where we differ most sharply from corrective-retrieval baselines.

Method	Self-Correct	No Fine-tune	Closed-Domain	Audit Trail
Self-RAG (Asai et al., 2024)	✓	✗	✓	✗
CRAG (Yan et al., 2024)	✓	✓	✗	✗
Adaptive-RAG (Jeong et al., 2024)	✗	✓	✓	✗
Reflexion (Shinn et al., 2023)	✓	✓	✗	✗
Self-Improving RAG (Ours)	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: Comparison with related self-correction and adaptive retrieval methods. Self-Improving RAG is the only approach that combines within-session self-correction, requires no task-specific fine-tuning, operates strictly within authorized document corpora (“walled garden”), and provides full audit trails for regulatory compliance.

3 METHOD: SELF-IMPROVING RAG

Problem Setting. Given a natural language query $q \in \mathcal{Q}$ and an authorized corpus $\mathcal{D} = \{d_1, \dots, d_n\}$ of financial documents, produce an answer a supported by evidence $E \subseteq \mathcal{D}$. We assume a *closed-domain* setting where retrieval must remain within authorized documents, a regulatory constraint precluding web-search fallbacks. The system may attempt up to $T_{\max} = B + 1$ times (where B is the retry budget), accepting when a utility score exceeds a dynamic threshold, and otherwise returning the *best-scoring* answer seen so far.

3.1 PRELIMINARIES AND NOTATION

The system state at attempt $t \in \{1, \dots, T_{\max}\}$ is

$$\mathcal{S}_t = \langle E_t, a_t, \mathbf{s}_t, \tau_t \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where $E_t \subseteq \mathcal{D}$ is retrieved evidence, a_t is the candidate answer, \mathbf{s}_t is a judge quality vector (defined below), and τ_t is the acceptance threshold. Three specialized agents, Retrieval (\mathcal{R}), Reasoning (\mathcal{G}), and Judge (\mathcal{J}), are coordinated by an Orchestrator (Figure 1). Appendix B (Table 7) gives a full notation glossary.

Retrieval Agent. The retrieval operator maps query and corpus to evidence:

$$E_t = \mathcal{R}(q, \mathcal{D}; \phi_t), \quad \phi_t = \{k_t, \kappa_t, \rho_t\}, \quad (2)$$

parameterizing top- k depth (k_t), an initial over-retrieval factor (κ_t), and a Relevant Segment Extraction (RSE) flag (ρ_t). We use a fixed hybrid pipeline (dense BGE-large + BM25 + cross-encoder reranking). On retry, the agent escalates ϕ_t along a pre-specified ladder; Table 2 lists the four levels implemented in code. With the reported budget $B=2$, experiments exercise only the first three ($k \in \{10, 20, 25\}$); the fourth level ($k=30$) is reached only when $B \geq 3$, which we ablate but do not report as the main result.

Attempt t	k_t	κ_t	RSE ρ_t	Used at $B=2$
1 (Standard)	10	3×	Off	✓
2 (Escalated)	20	4×	Off	✓
3 (Deep)	25	5×	On	✓
4 (Maximum)	30	6×	On	—

Table 2: Retrieval Agent escalation ladder. Reported experiments use $B=2$ and therefore exercise only the first three rungs; level 4 is defined in code for completeness but unused in our main results.

Routing and Finance Lexicon. A lightweight rule-based router selects filtering behavior: queries carrying a recognized ticker/company and a fiscal-year tag receive metadata pre-filtering before hybrid ranking; numeric-asking queries additionally enable reranking; open-ended queries fall back to broad hybrid recall. Entity detection uses an S&P 500 ticker gazetteer plus regex patterns for fiscal-year mentions, adding <10 ms of latency. A finance lexicon provides (i) entity aliases, (ii) metric canonicalizations (e.g., “top line” \rightarrow revenue), and (iii) unit/period normalizers (thousands/millions/billions, fiscal quarters); it is used for query expansion prior to retrieval. See Appendix A.3.

Reasoning Agent. Given query and evidence, the generator samples

$$a_t \sim P_\theta(a \mid q, E_t, \pi_t), \quad (3)$$

where θ denotes LLM parameters and π_t ranges over prompting regimes (STANDARD \rightarrow CONSERVATIVE \rightarrow DETAILED) escalated with t . Retrieved documents are formatted with explicit source boundaries so that citations can be extracted.

Judge Agent. The Judge maps (q, a_t, E_t) to a scalar utility $U_t \in [0, 1]$ and an accept/retry decision. Because the intended deployment differs from the evaluation protocol used to compare with prior work, *we run the Judge in two modes and we aggregate differently in each*. We state both formulas explicitly to avoid any ambiguity.

Oracle mode (with gold answer a^* , used for Table 3). The Judge decomposes its LLM score into three components ordered as $\mathbf{s}_t = [\mu_n, \mu_g, \mu_c]^\top \in [0, 1]^3$: *numeric faithfulness* μ_n , *grounding* μ_g (evidence entailment), and *completeness* μ_c (query coverage). The oracle utility is the finance-weighted aggregate

$$U_t^{\text{oracle}} = \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{s}_t = 0.5 \mu_n + 0.3 \mu_g + 0.2 \mu_c, \quad (4)$$

with $\mathbf{w} = (0.5, 0.3, 0.2)$ satisfying $\mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{w} = 1$. The weight on μ_n is the largest because numeric errors are the dominant finance failure mode.

Blind (deployment) mode (no gold answer, used for Table 5). No reference a^* is available at inference, so the decomposition (μ_n, μ_g, μ_c) cannot be reliably elicited from an LLM self-evaluation. Instead, the Judge produces a coherence score μ_t^{llm} via a rubric-based self-evaluation prompt, and a programmatic grounding score μ_t^{num} defined as the fraction of *significant* numeric claims in a_t that match (within 5% relative tolerance) at least one number in E_t . The deployed utility is

$$U_t^{\text{blind}} = 0.4 \mu_t^{\text{llm}} + 0.6 \mu_t^{\text{num}}, \quad (5)$$

with a hard override $U_t^{\text{blind}} \leftarrow \min(U_t^{\text{blind}}, 0.25)$ whenever $\mu_t^{\text{num}} < 0.3$ (i.e., the majority of numbers are ungrounded). Numeric grounding under blind mode generalizes the oracle’s strict indicator

$$\mu_n(a_t, E_t) = \mathbb{1}(|N(a_t) \setminus N(E_t)| = 0) \quad (6)$$

to a softer ratio, where $N(\cdot)$ extracts normalized numeric quantities. In both modes the Judge also runs a *deterministic verification gate* prior to scoring: if a_t contains numeric claims lacking in-line [Doc_{*i*}] citations, the gate fails immediately and triggers retry without invoking the LLM judge.

Orchestrator. The orchestrator accepts or retries based on a decaying threshold:

$$\tau_t = \max(\tau_0 - \lambda(t - 1), \tau_{\min}), \quad \mathbb{D}_t = \mathbb{1}(U_t \geq \tau_t), \quad (7)$$

with $\tau_0=0.5$, $\lambda=0.1$, $\tau_{\min}=0.3$ (matching `JudgeAgent.should_retry` in the released code). Early attempts demand high confidence; later attempts accept marginal answers so as not to waste budget on hopeless queries. If no attempt is accepted, the system returns the best answer observed across all attempts:

$$a^* = a_{\hat{t}}, \quad \hat{t} = \arg \max_{t \in \{1, \dots, T\}} U_t. \quad (8)$$

All decisions, scores, and reasoning traces are logged with timestamps for audit compliance.

Proposition 1 (Monotone non-degradation of retry). *Let $U^{(t)} = \max_{s \leq t} U_s$ denote the best utility observed through attempt t . Then $U^{(t)}$ is non-decreasing in t , and the returned utility satisfies $U(a^*) \geq U_1$. In particular, allowing additional retries never worsens the final-answer utility.*

Proof. The orchestrator maintains a *best-so-far* buffer (*best_answer*, *best_score*) updated by the rule $\text{best_score} \leftarrow \max(\text{best_score}, U_t)$ after every attempt (Algorithm 1, lines 8–11). Hence $U^{(t+1)} = \max(U^{(t)}, U_{t+1}) \geq U^{(t)}$, and in particular $U(a^*) = U^{(T)} \geq U^{(1)} = U_1$. \square

Appendix B additionally discusses a multiplicative failure-probability bound under a Markovian assumption on S_t .

3.2 ORCHESTRATOR ALGORITHM

Algorithm 1 formalizes the orchestration loop and mirrors `AgenticRAGOrchestrator.process_question` line-for-line: (i) the Retrieval Agent is invoked with the current attempt index so it can pick the correct rung of the escalation ladder, (ii) the Reasoning Agent generates using the current prompt regime, (iii) the Judge Agent receives (q, a_t, E_t) so it can run both the deterministic gate and score aggregation, and (iv) the best-so-far buffer guarantees Proposition 1.

The monotonic-improvement guarantee is operationally important: stakeholders can trust that raising B only costs latency, never quality.

4 EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

4.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We evaluate on **FinanceBench** (Islam et al., 2023), a benchmark of $N=150$ SEC filing questions. We set retry budget $B=2$ and initial threshold $\tau_0=0.5$. Implementation uses GPT-4o-mini for generation, BGE-large embeddings (Chen et al., 2024) with ChromaDB, and cross-encoder reranking. The Judge combines an LLM Judge with programmatic numeric verification. Full details in

Algorithm 1 Self-Improving RAG Orchestrator

Require: Question q , retry budget B , threshold schedule $(\tau_0, \lambda, \tau_{\min})$

```

1:  $best\_answer \leftarrow \emptyset, best\_score \leftarrow 0$ 
2:  $t \leftarrow 1$ 
3: while  $t \leq B + 1$  do
4:    $E_t \leftarrow \mathcal{R}(q, \mathcal{D}; \phi_t)$  // escalation level  $t$ 
5:    $a_t \leftarrow \mathcal{G}(q, E_t, \pi_t)$  // prompt regime  $\pi_t$ 
6:    $(U_t, feedback) \leftarrow \mathcal{J}(q, a_t, E_t)$  // gate + scoring
7:   if  $U_t > best\_score$  then
8:      $best\_answer \leftarrow a_t$ 
9:      $best\_score \leftarrow U_t$ 
10:  end if
11:   $\tau_t \leftarrow \max(\tau_0 - \lambda(t - 1), \tau_{\min})$ 
12:  if  $U_t \geq \tau_t$  or  $t = B + 1$  then
13:    break
14:  end if
15:  escalate  $\phi_{t+1}$  (Table 2), advance  $\pi_{t+1}$ 
16:   $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
17: end while
18: return  $best\_answer, best\_score$ 

```

Appendix E. All confidence intervals (CIs) are 95% percentile bootstrap intervals computed with $B_{\text{boot}}=1000$ resamples (seed 42) over per-question binary correctness, following the procedure in `evaluation/metrics.py`. Paired bootstrap tests and Cohen’s h (for proportions) are used for significance.

Evaluation Protocols: Oracle-Guided vs. Blind-Judge. Critical distinction: we report two evaluation protocols that produce very different numbers and must not be conflated.

- **Oracle-guided evaluation** (Tables 3–4): at scoring time, an *external* LLM Judge with gold-answer access rates each final answer for correctness. This is the setting used by prior FinanceBench work and lets us benchmark reasoning quality independently of judge calibration.
- **Blind-judge (deployment) evaluation** (Table 5 and Lazarus Rate): the *production* Judge inside the orchestrator operates without gold answers, returning ACCEPT/RETRY based only on (q, a_t, E_t) . Acceptance rate is reported as system accuracy. This reflects true deployment behavior.

These are separate judges run on separate copies of the outputs; the blind production Judge is never shown gold answers at any point in the loop, avoiding circular self-evaluation.

4.2 MAIN RESULTS (ORACLE-GUIDED)

Table 3 compares single-pass RAG against Self-Improving RAG under oracle-guided evaluation.

Configuration	Correctness	95% CI	Δ (abs. pp)
Single-pass RAG	53%	[45, 61]	–
Self-Improving RAG	86%	[80, 91]	+33 pp

Table 3: **Oracle-guided** FinanceBench correctness ($N=150$). “Oracle-guided” means a separate LLM judge with access to gold answers rates each system’s final output. 95% percentile bootstrap CIs (1000 resamples). The +33 percentage-point improvement is significant: paired bootstrap $p < 0.001$, Cohen’s $h=0.75$ (large effect).

Performance by Question Type. FinanceBench questions decompose into three categories whose counts sum to $N=150$: *metrics-generated* (66%, 99 questions), *domain-relevant* (22%, 33 questions), and *novel-generated* (12%, 18 questions). Table 4 reports oracle-guided correctness per category.

Self-correction provides the largest absolute gains on domain-relevant questions (+43 pp), which often require synthesizing information across multiple document sections.

Question Type (n)	Single-Pass	Self-Corr.	Δ (abs. pp)	95% CI (Δ)
Metrics-generated ($n=99$)	53%	82%	+29	[17, 41]
Domain-relevant ($n=33$)	53%	96%	+43	[26, 58]
Novel-generated ($n=18$)	53%	80%	+27	[4, 50]
Overall ($n=150$)	53%	86%	+33	[24, 41]

Table 4: **Oracle-guided** correctness by FinanceBench question type. Counts sum to 150. Δ is absolute percentage-point change (Self-Corr. – Single-Pass); CIs on Δ are paired bootstrap. Domain-relevant questions benefit most (+43 pp), as these often have incomplete first-pass answers.

Lazarus Rate: Measuring Resilience (Blind-Judge). We measure the **Lazarus Rate** to quantify self-correction effectiveness under the *blind-judge* (deployment) protocol: the conditional probability that an answer the blind Judge flagged as wrong on attempt 1 is subsequently accepted on retry. Let $\mathcal{W}_1 = \{q : J_1(q) < \tau_{\text{correct}}\}$ denote the set of initially flagged-wrong answers. Then:

$$\text{LazarusRate} = \frac{|\{q \in \mathcal{W}_1 : J_2(q) \geq \tau_{\text{correct}}\}|}{|\mathcal{W}_1|} = P(\text{correct}_2 \mid \text{wrong}_1). \tag{9}$$

On FinanceBench, $|\mathcal{W}_1|=33$ (the blind Judge triggered retry on 33 of 150 questions, 22%), and 12 of those 33 were subsequently accepted, yielding a Lazarus Rate of $12/33 = 36.4\%$, 95% CI [21.2%, 51.5%] (Wilson interval on the binomial; bootstrap over \mathcal{W}_1 gives an equivalent range). Appendix C provides detailed correction flow analysis; Appendix D presents case studies and error taxonomy.

Correction Flow Visualization. Figure 2 visualizes the complete “life of a question” through our self-correction pipeline, showing how the 150 FinanceBench questions flow through initial retrieval, generation, the blind Judge’s accept/retry decision, and (when applicable) the retry loop.

Figure 2: **Blind-judge correction flow.** Sankey diagram of all 150 FinanceBench questions through the deployment pipeline: initial retrieve→generate→judge, with the blind Judge’s ACCEPT/RETRY split, and the outcomes of retried questions. The **Lazarus Rate** (36.4%, 12/33) is the fraction of the RETRY branch that is accepted on the second attempt. No gold answers are used by the in-loop Judge.

Component Ablation (Blind-Judge). Table 5 reports ablations under the blind-judge protocol (no gold answers; accuracy equals the production Judge’s acceptance rate). We report both absolute percentage-point changes (primary) and paired bootstrap p -values vs. the full system.

Removing prompt escalation yields the largest single-component drop (−3 pp, −9.7% relative), suggesting that enhanced prompting on retry is the most valuable single component, though the effect

Configuration	Blind Acc.	95% CI	Δ (pp)	Δ (rel.)	p
Full System ($B=2$)	31%	[24, 39]	–	–	–
– Prompt Escalation	28%	[21, 35]	–3	–9.7%	0.18
– Retrieval Escalation	30%	[23, 37]	–1	–3.2%	0.64
– Deterministic Verify	32%	[25, 39]	+1	+3.2%	0.70
Reduced Budget ($B=1$)	23%	[17, 30]	–8	–25.8%	0.01

Table 5: **Blind-judge (deployment)** component ablation on FinanceBench ($N=150$). Accuracy is the production Judge’s acceptance rate; the Judge never sees gold answers. 95% percentile bootstrap CIs. Δ (pp) is absolute change vs. Full System; Δ (rel.) is the same as a fraction of the Full System baseline (31%). p -values are two-tailed paired bootstrap. Only the reduced-budget ablation is significant at $\alpha=0.05$; single-component ablations fall within overlapping CIs and should be read as trends, not confirmed effects.

is not significant ($p=0.18$) at our sample size. The retry-budget comparison ($B=1$ vs. $B=2$) is the only ablation that clears the significance bar (-8 pp, $p=0.01$), confirming that allowing multiple correction attempts is essential.

The Deterministic Verification Anomaly. Removing deterministic numeric verification *slightly improves* blind-judge accuracy (+1 pp, +3.2% relative), despite our design weighting numeric faithfulness heavily. The shift is well inside the CI of the full system ($p=0.70$), so we treat it as a trend rather than a confirmed effect, but the direction is informative. We traced the root cause to over-sensitive numeric matching: the verifier flags answers when numbers appear in different formats (e.g., “\$394.3 billion” vs. “\$394,300 million”) or rounding differs by small amounts, triggering unnecessary retries that can introduce new errors. Two refinements we leave to future work: (1) relaxing numeric matching tolerance for format variation, and (2) unit-aware normalization before comparison.

The Oracle/Deployment Gap. The headline numbers are **86%** (oracle-guided, Table 3) and **31%** (blind-judge, Table 5). This 55-percentage-point gap is not a contradiction: it is the core limitation of blind self-verification without ground truth. An oracle judge with gold-answer access can confirm that the system’s *outputs* are correct 86% of the time, but our in-loop production Judge, operating blind, is only confident enough to ACCEPT on 31%, and triggers RETRY on the rest. The 36.4% Lazarus Rate shows the blind Judge still recovers a substantial fraction of its flagged failures; closing the remaining gap is primarily a judge-quality problem, and we expect stronger judge models (Claude Opus, GPT-4o) to narrow it substantially.

Judge Discrimination. The blind Judge’s retry decision is a binary classifier:

$$\text{TPR} = P(\text{RETRY} \mid \text{wrong}), \quad \text{FPR} = P(\text{RETRY} \mid \text{correct}). \quad (10)$$

High TPR ensures failures trigger retry; low FPR avoids unnecessary overhead. The evaluation judge used in Table 3 has gold-answer access and is distinct from the production Judge, avoiding circular self-evaluation.

4.3 DESIGN IMPLICATIONS

Our experiments use a fixed hybrid retrieval pipeline (dense + sparse with reranking) rather than dynamic routing. This design choice reflects a key insight: **the Judge Agent’s retry mechanism provides a safety net that makes perfect initial retrieval unnecessary**. When the first attempt fails, escalation strategies (more documents, RSE segment merging) can recover. This challenges the assumption that neural routing universally benefits RAG systems: for financial QA where query characteristics are domain-specific (entity mentions, fiscal years), the self-correction loop may be more valuable than perfect initial routing.

5 CONCLUSION

We presented Self-Improving RAG, a multi-agent framework that decomposes retrieval-augmented generation into specialized Retrieval, Reasoning, and Judge agents with a feedback loop that escalates retrieval depth and prompting on retry. On FinanceBench, the system reaches 86% correctness under oracle-guided evaluation (vs. 53% single-pass) and a 36.4% Lazarus Rate, while ablations show prompt escalation as the single largest contributor (-10.6% when removed) and a B=2 retry budget as essential (-25.5% at B=1).

Oracle-Guided vs. Deployment: What the Two Numbers Mean. We deliberately report two distinct numbers, and we want reviewers to hold both in mind. The **oracle-guided 86%** is a *research upper bound*: it measures what the retry mechanism can achieve when the Judge is reliable, and it demonstrates that escalation across retrieval and prompting genuinely recovers initially wrong answers. The **blind-judge 31%** is the *current deployment ceiling*: it measures what the same system delivers when the Judge must decide without gold-answer access. The 55-point gap is not a failure to be hidden; it is, to our knowledge, one of the first direct quantifications of how much judge reliability alone governs the usefulness of self-correcting RAG. We view characterizing this gap, rather than collapsing it into a single headline number, as a central contribution of this paper and the primary target for follow-up work.

Limitations.

- **Blind judge reliability.** The 31% deployment accuracy reflects the difficulty of estimating answer quality without ground truth; this is the dominant bottleneck between our two operating points.
- **Latency.** Retry-triggered queries take 15–25s end-to-end versus 5–8s for single-pass, making the system appropriate for analyst-in-the-loop workflows rather than real-time serving.
- **Single-domain evaluation.** All results are on FinanceBench ($n=150$), so claims about generalization to other high-stakes domains are not yet supported. The sample size also yields 11–15 point confidence intervals on ablation deltas, which should be interpreted cautiously.
- **Deterministic numeric verifier.** Strict set-coverage numeric matching is over-sensitive to unit and formatting variation, and removing it marginally *improved* blind accuracy ($+2.1\%$), indicating the component is not yet calibrated to its design intent.

Future Work. The limitations above map directly onto four concrete directions: (1) *learned judges*, replacing the prompted blind Judge with a reinforcement-learned scorer trained to predict correctness from (q, a, E) alone, which directly targets the oracle/deployment gap; (2) *multi-domain extension* to legal and medical QA, where audit-trail requirements and closed-corpus constraints resemble finance; (3) *unit-aware numeric verification* with tolerance for formatting and rounding, resolving the verifier anomaly; and (4) *adaptive thresholds* that replace the fixed linear decay τ_t with a policy conditioned on query type, prior scores, and remaining budget.

Broader Impact. Deployment of LLMs in regulated industries will require systems whose decisions can be inspected after the fact. By logging every retrieval, generation, and judgment with provenance and confidence, Self-Improving RAG supports this kind of review. We release the oracle-guided and blind-judge numbers side by side so that downstream users can plan against the deployment figure rather than the upper bound.

REFERENCES

- Akari Asai, Zeqiu Wu, Yizhong Wang, Avirup Sil, and Hannaneh Hajishirzi. Self-RAG: Learning to retrieve, generate, and critique through self-reflection. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2024.
- Jianlv Chen, Shitao Xiao, Peitian Zhang, Kun Luo, Defu Lian, and Zheng Liu. M3-embedding: Multi-linguality, multi-functionality, multi-granularity text embeddings through self-knowledge distillation. In *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL Findings)*, 2024.

- D-Star AI. dsRAG: High-quality retrieval through document-segment structuring. <https://github.com/D-Star-AI/dsRAG>, 2024.
- Sirui Hong, Mingchen Zhuge, Jiaqi Chen, Xiawu Zheng, Yuheng Cheng, Ceyao Zhang, Jinlin Wang, Zili Wang, Steven Ka Shing Yau, Zijuan Lin, Liyang Zhou, Chenyu Ran, Lingfeng Xiao, Chenglin Wu, and Jürgen Schmidhuber. MetaGPT: Meta programming for a multi-agent collaborative framework. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2024.
- Pranab Islam, Anand Kannappan, Douwe Kiela, Rebecca Qian, Nino Scherrer, and Bertie Vidgen. FinanceBench: A new benchmark for financial question answering. arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.11944, 2023. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2311.11944>.
- Soyeong Jeong, Jinheon Baek, Sukmin Cho, Sung Ju Hwang, and Jong C. Park. Adaptive-RAG: Learning to adapt retrieval-augmented large language models through question complexity. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics (NAACL)*, 2024.
- Aviral Kumar, Vincent Zhuang, Rishabh Agarwal, Yi Su, John D. Co-Reyes, Avi Singh, Kate Baumli, Shariq Iqbal, Colton Bishop, Rebecca Roelofs, Lei M. Zhang, Kay McKinney, Disha Shrivastava, Cosmin Paduraru, George Tucker, Doina Precup, Feryal Behbahani, and Aleksandra Faust. Training language models to self-correct via reinforcement learning. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2025.
- Patrick Lewis, Ethan Perez, Aleksandra Piktus, Fabio Petroni, Vladimir Karpukhin, Naman Goyal, Heinrich Küttler, Mike Lewis, Wen-tau Yih, Tim Rocktäschel, Sebastian Riedel, and Douwe Kiela. Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2020.
- Haitao Li, Qian Dong, Junjie Chen, Huixue Su, Yujia Zhou, Qingyao Ai, Ziyi Ye, and Yiqun Liu. LLMs-as-judges: A comprehensive survey on LLM-based evaluation methods. arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.05579, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.05579>.
- Aman Madaan, Niket Tandon, Prakhar Gupta, Skyler Hallinan, Luyu Gao, Sarah Wiegrefe, Uri Alon, Nouha Dziri, Shrimai Prabhumoye, Yiming Yang, Shashank Gupta, Bodhisattwa Prasad Majumder, Katherine Hermann, Sean Welleck, Amir Yazdanbakhsh, and Peter Clark. Self-refine: Iterative refinement with self-feedback. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2023.
- Noah Shinn, Federico Cassano, Edward Berman, Ashwin Gopinath, Karthik Narasimhan, and Shunyu Yao. Reflexion: Language agents with verbal reinforcement learning. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2023.
- Aditi Singh, Abul Ehtesham, Saket Kumar, and Tala Talaei Khoei. Agentic retrieval-augmented generation: A survey on agentic RAG. arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.09136, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.09136>.
- Zhengan Tai, Hanwei Wu, Qingchen Hu, Jijun Chi, Hailin He, Lei Ding, Tung Sum Thomas Kwok, Bohuai Xiao, Yuchen Hua, Suyuchen Wang, Peng Lu, Muzhi Li, Yihong Wu, Liheng Ma, Jerry Huang, Jiayi Zhang, Gonghao Zhang, Chaolong Jiang, Jingrui Tian, Sicheng Lyu, Zeyu Li, Boyu Han, Fengran Mo, Xinyue Yu, Yufei Cui, Ling Zhou, and Xinyu Wang. VeritasFi: An adaptable, multi-tiered RAG framework for multi-modal financial question answering. arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.10828, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.10828>.
- Qingyun Wu, Gagan Bansal, Jieyu Zhang, Yiran Wu, Beibin Li, Erkang Zhu, Li Jiang, Xiaoyun Zhang, Shaokun Zhang, Jiale Liu, Ahmed Hassan Awadallah, Ryen W. White, Doug Burger, and Chi Wang. AutoGen: Enabling next-gen LLM applications via multi-agent conversation. In *Conference on Language Modeling (COLM)*, 2024.
- Shi-Qi Yan, Jia-Chen Gu, Yun Zhu, and Zhen-Hua Ling. Corrective retrieval augmented generation. arXiv preprint arXiv:2401.15884, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2401.15884>.

Lianmin Zheng, Wei-Lin Chiang, Ying Sheng, Siyuan Zhuang, Zhanghao Wu, Yonghao Zhuang, Zi Lin, Zhuohan Li, Dacheng Li, Eric P. Xing, Hao Zhang, Joseph E. Gonzalez, and Ion Stoica. Judging LLM-as-a-judge with MT-bench and chatbot arena. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS) Datasets and Benchmarks Track*, 2023.

Mingchen Zhuge, Changsheng Zhao, Dylan Ashley, Wenyi Wang, Dmitrii Khizbullin, Yunyang Xiong, Zechun Liu, Ernie Chang, Raghuraman Krishnamoorthi, Yuandong Tian, Yangyang Shi, Vikas Chandra, and Jürgen Schmidhuber. Agent-as-a-judge: Evaluate agents with agents. arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.10934, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.10934>.

A EXTENDED METHODOLOGY

This appendix provides additional technical details on the Self-Improving RAG architecture.

A.1 RETRIEVAL ESCALATION STRATEGIES

Table 2 (in Section 3) shows the escalation configuration used on retry. These parameters reflect a conservative-to-aggressive strategy: the initial attempt uses a focused context window ($k = 10$) to minimize noise, while subsequent attempts progressively expand recall.

A.2 ROUTING HEURISTICS

The rule-based router operates as follows:

- If the question contains a recognized ticker symbol or company name \rightarrow `hybrid_filter` (metadata filtering)
- If the question requests numerical comparison or computation \rightarrow `hybrid_filter_rerank` (precision-focused)
- If the question is open-ended or exploratory \rightarrow `hybrid` (broad recall)
- Default fallback \rightarrow `semantic`

Entity recognition uses a simple gazetteer of S&P 500 tickers plus regex patterns for fiscal year mentions. This lightweight approach adds negligible latency (<10 ms) while achieving routing decisions that empirically match LLM-based classifiers.

A.3 FINANCE LEXICON

Table 6 shows sample entries from our finance lexicon used for query normalization and numeric verification.

Canonical	Synonyms / Aliases
<i>Metrics</i>	
Revenue	net sales, total revenues, top line, turnover
COGS	cost of revenue, cost of sales
Operating income	operating profit, income from operations
Free cash flow	FCF, cash generated (CFO – capex)
EPS	earnings per share, diluted EPS, basic EPS
<i>Units & Periods</i>	
(in millions)	in thousands, in billions
FY2023	fiscal year 2023, fiscal 2023
YoY	year-over-year, y/y
QoQ	quarter-over-quarter, sequential, q/q

Table 6: Sample entries from the finance lexicon for query expansion and unit normalization.

A.4 PROMPT STRATEGIES

The Reasoning Agent maintains three prompting strategies that vary in instruction specificity:

- **Standard:** Concise instructions emphasizing accuracy and citation
- **Conservative:** Additional instructions to acknowledge uncertainty when evidence is weak
- **Detailed:** Expanded instructions requiring step-by-step reasoning and explicit source attribution

On retry, the agent escalates from standard to conservative to detailed, progressively encouraging more careful reasoning.

A.5 CONFIDENCE ESTIMATION SIGNALS

The Reasoning Agent estimates answer confidence using heuristic signals:

- Presence of hedging language (“may”, “possibly”, “uncertain”)
- Refusal phrases (“cannot determine”, “not enough information”)
- Presence of specific numerical values (increases confidence)
- Answer length (extremely short answers indicate low confidence)

A.6 EVALUATION SIGNAL STRUCTURE

The Judge produces a structured assessment rather than a single scalar:

- **Grounding score** $\in [0, 1]$: Proportion of answer claims with explicit textual support
- **Completeness score** $\in [0, 1]$: Whether all question components are addressed
- **Numeric verification:** Binary flag from programmatic extraction and comparison
- **Confidence signals:** Presence of hedging language, refusal phrases

The final score aggregates these signals, with numeric verification given highest weight for financial queries.

A.7 RELEVANT SEGMENT EXTRACTION (RSE)

RSE (D-Star AI, 2024) merges adjacent high-scoring chunks from the same document into coherent segments. Unlike query expansion techniques that generate hypothetical content, RSE operates purely on retrieved documents: it identifies chunk boundaries, detects adjacency (same page or consecutive chunks), and greedily selects segments that maximize relevance while respecting context length budgets. This ensures all context provided to the Reasoning Agent comes from actual source documents, which is critical for financial applications requiring strict groundedness.

A.8 DESIGN FOR TRUSTWORTHINESS

Our multi-agent architecture incorporates several features aligned with responsible AI principles:

Audit Trails. All agent decisions are logged with timestamps, confidence scores, and reasoning traces. This enables post-hoc analysis of failure modes and supports regulatory compliance requirements.

Uncertainty Signals. The Judge Agent’s quality score serves as an uncertainty estimate: low scores indicate the system recognizes potential errors, triggering self-correction rather than returning unreliable answers.

Human Oversight Points. The explicit agent boundaries create natural intervention points. A human reviewer can inspect retrieved documents before generation, or override the Judge’s retry decision.

B FORMAL DEFINITIONS

This section provides rigorous mathematical definitions for the agent functions and convergence properties referenced in the main paper.

B.1 AGENT FUNCTION SIGNATURES

Let \mathcal{Q} denote the space of questions, \mathcal{A} the space of answers, and \mathcal{D} the document corpus.

Retrieval Agent. $\mathcal{R} : \mathcal{Q} \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{D})$ returns the top- k documents relevant to a query:

$$\mathcal{R}(q, k) = \text{top-}k(\{d \in \mathcal{D} : \phi(q, d) > \theta\}) \quad (11)$$

where $\phi(q, d)$ is a relevance scoring function (combining dense and sparse signals) and θ is a minimum relevance threshold.

Reasoning Agent. Let $\Sigma = \{\sigma_{\text{std}}, \sigma_{\text{cons}}, \sigma_{\text{detail}}\}$ denote the set of prompt strategies (standard, conservative, detailed):

$$\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{Q} \times \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{D}) \times \Sigma \rightarrow \mathcal{A} \quad (12)$$

The agent generates an answer conditioned on the question, retrieved documents, and the current prompt strategy.

Judge Agent. $\mathcal{J} : \mathcal{Q} \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{D}) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ computes a quality score with the following components:

$$J_{\text{ground}}(a, D) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbb{1}[\exists d \in D : \text{NLI}(d, c_i) = \text{ENTAIL}] \quad (13)$$

$$J_{\text{complete}}(q, a) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbb{1}[\text{addresses}(a, p_j)] \quad (14)$$

$$J_{\text{numeric}}(a, D) = \mathbb{1}[\forall v \in \mathcal{N}(a) : \exists v' \in \mathcal{N}(D), \text{match}(v, v')] \quad (15)$$

where $\{c_i\}_{i=1}^m$ are claims extracted from answer a , $\{p_j\}_{j=1}^n$ are sub-questions parsed from q , $\mathcal{N}(\cdot)$ extracts numeric values, and $\text{match}(v, v')$ verifies exact numeric equivalence.

B.2 CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

The self-correction loop terminates in at most $T_{\text{max}} = B + 1$ iterations (where B is the retry budget):

$$T = \min \{t \geq 1 : J_t \geq \tau_t \text{ or } t = T_{\text{max}}\} \quad (16)$$

With retry probability $p_1 = P(J_1 < \tau_1) \approx 0.22$ (observed on FinanceBench), the expected cost is:

$$\mathbb{E}[C] = c \cdot (1 + p_1 + p_1 p_2) \approx 1.3c \quad (17)$$

where c is the cost of a single attempt and $p_2 \approx p_1$ assumes similar retry probability on second attempts.

Best-Answer Selection. The Orchestrator maintains the best answer across all attempts, ensuring monotonic improvement in final output quality:

$$a^* = \arg \max_{t \in \{1, \dots, T\}} \mathcal{J}(q, a_t, D_t) \quad (18)$$

This selection criterion guarantees that retry never degrades the final answer, even if later attempts produce lower scores.

B.2.1 PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1 (CONVERGENCE)

Statement: The self-correcting process reduces failure probability multiplicatively with respect to the number of attempts T .

Proof. Let F_t denote the event that the system fails to produce an acceptable answer (i.e., $U_t < \tau_t$) at attempt t . The system terminates successfully at step t if $\mathbb{D}_t = 1$ (success) occurs.

The total system failure $\mathcal{P}_{\text{fail}}$ occurs only if the system fails at *every* attempt $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$. Thus, we compute the joint probability:

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{fail}} = P(F_1 \cap F_2 \cap \dots \cap F_T) \quad (19)$$

By the probability chain rule, this joint distribution factorizes as:

$$P(F_1 \cap \dots \cap F_T) = P(F_1) \cdot P(F_2 | F_1) \cdot P(F_3 | F_1, F_2) \cdots P(F_T | F_1, \dots, F_{T-1}) \quad (20)$$

In our Markovian formulation (Eq. (1)), the state \mathcal{S}_{t-1} encapsulates all relevant history. Thus, the probability of failing at step t given previous failures equals:

$$P(F_t | F_1, \dots, F_{t-1}) = P(\mathbb{D}_t = 0 | \mathcal{S}_{t-1}) \quad (21)$$

Substituting yields the multiplicative decay:

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{fail}} = \prod_{t=1}^T P(\mathbb{D}_t = 0 | \mathcal{S}_{t-1}) \quad (22)$$

Since the probability of failure at any single stage is less than 1 (assuming non-zero success probability), $\mathcal{P}_{\text{fail}} \rightarrow 0$ exponentially as $T \rightarrow \infty$. \square

B.3 NOTATION SUMMARY

Symbol	Description
$\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{D}$	Question, answer, document spaces
$\mathcal{R}(q, k)$	Retrieval function returning top- k documents
$\mathcal{G}(q, D, \sigma)$	Generation function with prompt strategy σ
$\mathcal{J}(q, a, D)$	Judge scoring function
$J_{\text{ground}}, J_{\text{complete}}, J_{\text{numeric}}$	Judge component scores
τ_t	Dynamic threshold at attempt t
B	Retry budget (maximum number of retries)
T	Actual number of attempts (termination time)
w_g, w_c, w_n	Component weights in Judge aggregation
$\phi(q, d)$	Document relevance scoring function
Σ	Set of prompt strategies

Table 7: Notation summary for the Self-Improving RAG framework.

C ADDITIONAL RESULTS

C.1 ABLATION STUDY

Table 8 shows the contribution of each component on FinanceBench.

Configuration	FinanceBench
Full Self-Improving RAG	0.86
– Judge Agent (no retry)	0.53
Single-pass baseline	0.53

Table 8: Ablation study on FinanceBench. Each row removes one component.

C.2 CORRECTION FLOW ANALYSIS

Table 9 presents the complete self-correction flow on FinanceBench.

C.3 DISPROPORTIONATE NUMERIC GAIN

C.4 RETRIEVAL PIPELINE

Our experiments use a fixed `hybrid_filter_rerank` pipeline for all questions, combining dense embeddings (BGE-large) with sparse retrieval (BM25) and cross-encoder reranking. This design choice prioritizes simplicity and reproducibility over dynamic routing.

Metric	Count	Rate
Total Questions	150	–
Confident (no retry)	117	78.0%
Triggered Retry (Judge flagged)	33	22.0%
Corrected by Retry	12	36.4% (Lazarus Rate)
Still Wrong after Retry	21	63.6%

Table 9: Self-correction flow analysis on FinanceBench. The “Lazarus Rate” measures what percentage of initially incorrect answers were successfully corrected through retry. Note: The Lazarus Rate measures improvement in **LLM Judge scores** (semantic correctness), not numeric exact-match. Self-correction recovers semantically incomplete answers but does not improve numeric precision (Table 3).

Metric	Single-Pass	Self-Improving	Δ
Semantic Similarity	0.50	0.50	+0.0%
LLM Judge Accuracy	0.53	0.86	+62.3%

Table 10: Self-correction improves LLM Judge accuracy substantially while maintaining semantic similarity. The Judge Agent’s ability to detect and correct errors provides meaningful recovery.

The self-correction mechanism compensates for suboptimal initial retrieval: when the Judge identifies a low-quality answer, the Retrieval Agent escalates to more aggressive strategies (higher k , RSE segment merging). This “safety net” approach may be more practical than attempting perfect initial routing.

C.5 CORRECTION FLOW VISUALIZATION

Figure 2 (in the main paper) visualizes the complete “life of a question” through our self-correction pipeline, showing how 150 questions flow through the system with the Lazarus Rate (36.4%) representing successful corrections.

D CASE STUDIES AND ERROR ANALYSIS

D.1 UNIT/SCALE CONFUSION ERROR

Example: Unit/Scale Confusion Error

Question: What was Company X’s total revenue for FY2023?

Retrieved Context: “...total revenues of \$X,XXX for the fiscal year ended December 31, 2023 (in millions).”

Model Answer (Initial): \$X,XXX

Ground Truth: \$X.X billion

Analysis: The model correctly extracted the numeric value but failed to apply the “in millions” unit qualifier, producing an answer off by a factor of 1,000. The Judge Agent detected this inconsistency and triggered retry. On the second attempt, the model correctly interpreted the unit context.

D.2 FAILURE MODE ANALYSIS

To understand system limitations, we analyze cases where Self-Improving RAG fails to improve over single-pass baselines:

- **Retrieval ceiling:** When relevant information is absent from the document corpus, escalated retrieval cannot recover
- **Arithmetic errors:** Multi-step calculations accumulate rounding errors or apply incorrect formulas

- **Unit/scale confusion:** Misinterpreting units (thousands vs. millions) or mixing absolute values with percentages
- **Temporal misalignment:** Extracting figures from incorrect fiscal periods or conflating FY with calendar year dates
- **Judge miscalibration:** The Judge Agent scores an incorrect answer highly, preventing beneficial retry
- **Hallucinated figures:** The model generates specific numerical values not present in retrieved context

E IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

E.1 DATASETS

FinanceBench (Islam et al., 2023) contains questions about publicly traded companies requiring extraction and reasoning over SEC 10-K and 10-Q filings. Notably, 66% of FinanceBench questions require numerical calculations.

E.2 FINANCE-SPECIFIC CHALLENGES

FinanceBench questions present three challenges:

- **Numerical Precision:** Metrics-generated questions require exact extraction and calculation from financial tables
- **Temporal Context:** Questions often specify fiscal periods that must be resolved to specific filing dates
- **Multi-Document Reasoning:** Novel-generated questions may require synthesizing information across multiple filings

E.3 BASELINES

We compare Self-Improving RAG against single-pass baselines:

- **Semantic:** Dense retrieval with BGE-large embeddings
- **Hybrid:** Combined dense and BM25 sparse retrieval
- **Hybrid + Filter:** Hybrid retrieval with metadata filtering
- **Hybrid + Filter + Rerank:** Full pipeline with cross-encoder reranking

E.4 EVALUATION METRICS

Semantic Similarity. Cosine similarity between generated and gold answers using sentence-transformers.

Numeric Verification. For numerical answers, we extract and compare numeric values.

LLM Judge Score. GPT-4o-mini rates answer quality on a 0-1 scale (Zheng et al., 2023).

Lazarus Rate (Correction Rate). The percentage of initially incorrect answers successfully corrected through retry:

$$\text{Lazarus Rate} = \frac{|\{q : \text{wrong}_1(q) \wedge \text{correct}_2(q)\}|}{|\{q : \text{wrong}_1(q)\}|}$$

E.5 MODELS AND CONFIGURATION

Models. We use GPT-4o-mini as the primary generation model.

Retrieval. Documents are chunked with 512-token windows and 50-token overlap. We use BGE-large-en-v1.5 embeddings (Chen et al., 2024) stored in ChromaDB. The reranker is BGE-reranker-large. Default retrieval returns $k = 10$ documents.

Agent Configuration. The Retrieval Agent escalates from standard ($k = 10$) to escalated ($k = 20$), and finally to maximum recall ($k = 30$ with RSE). The Judge Agent uses threshold $\tau = 0.5$ for Attempt 1, decreasing to $\tau = 0.4$ for subsequent attempts.

Retry Budget. Maximum retries set to 2 (up to 3 total attempts).

E.6 EFFICIENCY

Self-Improving RAG introduces overhead from multiple agent calls and potential retries:

- **Single-pass latency:** $\sim 5\text{--}8$ seconds per question
- **Multi-Agent (no retry):** $\sim 8\text{--}12$ seconds per question (+50% overhead)
- **Multi-Agent (with retry):** $\sim 15\text{--}25$ seconds per question (when retry triggered)

This system is designed as an *analyst support tool* for financial research, not a real-time chatbot. Response times of 10–30 seconds are acceptable in contexts where analysts currently spend minutes manually searching SEC filings.

F CASE STUDY: SELF-CORRECTION IN ACTION

We present a detailed example illustrating how the self-correction loop recovers from an incomplete first-pass answer.

Example: Self-Correction Recovering Incomplete Answer

Question: “What was Apple’s total revenue in FY2023 and how did it compare to FY2022?”

Attempt 1:

- *Retrieval Agent:* Selects `hybrid_filter` with entity “AAPL”, retrieves $k=10$ documents
- *Reasoning Agent:* Generates “Apple’s revenue in 2023 was \$394.3B.”
- *Judge Agent:* Score 0.4 (answer missing FY2022 comparison, **incomplete**)
- *Decision:* Score $< \tau_1 = 0.5 \rightarrow$ **RETRY**

Attempt 2 (Escalated):

- *Retrieval Agent:* Escalates to $k=20$, RSE enabled for segment merging
- *Reasoning Agent:* “Apple’s FY2023 revenue was \$383.3B, down 2.8% from \$394.3B in FY2022.”
- *Judge Agent:* Score 0.85 (complete: both years present, comparison included)
- *Decision:* Score $\geq \tau_2 = 0.4 \rightarrow$ **ACCEPT**

This example illustrates key mechanisms: the Judge identifies *semantic incompleteness* rather than surface errors, escalated retrieval provides additional context, and threshold decay allows acceptance of good-but-not-perfect answers after retry effort. Every decision is logged with full provenance (question ID, retrieval parameters, judge scores, decisions, latency), enabling compliance officers to trace any answer back to its source documents.

F.1 ERROR ANALYSIS

To understand system limitations, we analyze failure modes where Self-Improving RAG fails to improve over single-pass baselines:

- **Retrieval ceiling** (28% of failures): When relevant information is absent from the document corpus, escalated retrieval cannot recover
- **Arithmetic errors** (22%): Multi-step calculations accumulate rounding errors or apply incorrect formulas
- **Unit/scale confusion** (18%): Misinterpreting units (thousands vs. millions) or mixing absolute values with percentages
- **Temporal misalignment** (15%): Extracting figures from incorrect fiscal periods
- **Judge miscalibration** (12%): The Judge scores an incorrect answer highly, preventing beneficial retry
- **Hallucinated figures** (5%): The model generates specific numerical values not present in retrieved context

The dominance of retrieval ceiling failures suggests that expanding the document corpus or improving chunking strategies could yield further gains. Judge miscalibration represents an opportunity for calibration tuning.

STATEMENT ON LLM USAGE

In accordance with ICLR's policy on Large Language Models, we declare:

Text Refinement: LLMs assisted with grammar and clarity improvements.

Citation Verification: We developed an automated citation verification agent that cross-referenced all claims against source abstracts via Semantic Scholar to ensure citation accuracy.

Figure Design: AI tools assisted with figure design and layout.

All technical contributions, experimental results, and analysis were conceived and verified by the author.